

Effect of External Borrowing on Government Expenditure on Agriculture in Nigeria

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Abstract

Access to standard and efficient infrastructure facilities, for example road, healthcare, security, education, and power is a hallmark of a prosperous nation. However, this has become a cause of concern for the Nigeria citizens. The roads are death traps across major highways, access to basic primary heproductivitye is a challenge just as insecurity; Agricultural productivity as consistently remain poor and worsened by the activities of bandits. Finance experts have opined that with appropriate funding, such infrastructural deficit can be developed and made to improve economic activities which has positive ripple effect on living standard of the citizen. This study, therefore, examined the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure in the Nigerian agricultural sector. The model used was analysed within the ARDL framework and estimates were obtained in both the short and long run. The *ex-post facto* research design was used as a quantitative approach in this study to investigate the relationship between external debt, tax revenue, and infrastructure development. The data for this study is a time series trend from 1991 to 2022. The results of the long run estimate revealed that external borrowing has a negative and significant influence on government expenditure on agriculture, that is, a percentage

increase in external borrowing will reduce government expenditure on agriculture by 0.43 percent. For the short run estimates, one, two and three lagged values of government expenditure on agriculture significantly and positively influences the current value of government expenditure on agriculture. A percentage increase in these values will increase the current value of government expenditure on agriculture by 0.3, 0.2 and 0.2 percent respectively. External borrowing in the one, two and three lagged periods also significantly influence government expenditure on agriculture. It was recommended that the government diversify the source of external debt service, particularly to non-oil sectors such as agriculture, mining, industry, and manufacturing, in order to reduce the burden and negative consequences of Nigerians' overdependence on foreign exchange from oil and the volatility in its price.

Keywords: Agriculture infrastructure, External debt, Government expenditure, Multilateral debt

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Introduction

Countries borrow money when they do not have enough revenue to cover all of their spending needs (capital and recurrent) If the funds are used to expand the economy's productive potential, borrowing from abroad is a good idea and even required for speeding up infrastructure development (Okoli, 2019). Although Nigerians are eager to borrow money from abroad, this interest has yet to materialize into tangible improvements to the country's aging infrastructure. Initial evidence suggests that cash were either stolen or improperly spent (Acosta-Ormaechea & Morozumi, 2017).

For example, the Debt Management Office (DMO) requested to borrow additional N6. 39 trillion to cover the 2022 budget, bringing Nigeria's total indebtedness as of September 2022 to an estimated 44 trillion-Naira 2022 (The Debt Management Office, 2022). Nigeria's external borrowing rose to \$37.96 billion in the third quarter of 2021, from \$33.47 billion in the previous quarter (The Debt Management Office, 2022). In other words, \$16.74 billion came from multilateral debt, \$502.32 million from bilateral debt (AFD), and \$3.26 billion from bilateral debt issued by the Exim Bank of China, the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), the India Development Finance Corporation (IDFC), and the KFW. The remaining \$11.17 billion came from commercial debt instruments like Eurobonds and Diaspora Bonds (NBS, 2020). Unfortunately, Nigeria's infrastructural investment still ranks below average worldwide and average in Africa, suggesting that her massive

external borrowing profiles are not having a favorable effect on her infrastructural growth (GIIA, 2022).

Nigeria's infrastructure has not improved despite the country's use of various forms of external borrowing, including multilateral loans, bilateral loans, Eurobonds, and promissory notes (Hameed, Ashraf & Chaudhary, 2018). Unemployment, poverty, insecurity, want, kidnapping, terrorism, hunger, a poor economy, a weak naira, poor educational standards, rising inequality, increased inflation, banditry, social and political unrest, improper waste management, and higher child mortality rates are all results of Nigeria's subpar infrastructure, including its roads, agriculture, transportation, and economic services (Karagol, 2018; Malik, Hayat, 2015; Ogunmuyiwa, 2017; Oloyede, 2018; Soludo, 2018) Meanwhile, these international borrowing and infrastructure development face a corollary threat from the ongoing decline in the value of the naira, the increase in the interest rate for servicing loans, and the persistent rise in the prices of goods and services in general. Because a weaker naira may make exports to other countries less competitive.

Therefore, the study seeks to investigate the effect of Nigeria's external borrowing (multilateral debt, Eurobond, bilateral loan, and promissory note) on infrastructure development (agriculture and economic services) with inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate as control variables.

Statement of the Problem

Access to standard and efficient infrastructure facilities, for example road, healthcare, security, education, and power is a hallmark of a prosperous nation. However, this has become a cause of concern for the Nigeria citizens. The roads are death traps across major highways and in city centers, access to basic primary healthcare service is a challenge just as insecurity and an unrelenting industrial strike action embark upon by healthcare practitioners, university dons, and power generation employees happens too frequently. Agricultural productivity consistently remain poor and worsened by the activities of bandits. If the underlying concerns are not addressed, Nigeria is at risk of remaining a country with high levels of poverty.

Finance experts have opined that with appropriate funding, such infrastructural deficit can be developed and made to improve economic activities which has positive ripple effect on living standard of the citizen (Aladejana, Okeowo, Oluwalana & Alabi, 2021; GIIA, 2022; Okoli, 2019; Soludo, 2018; Todaro, 2018). While this sound logical, it is imperative to undertake empirical investigate to determine to what extent can funding drive

infrastructural development in Nigeria. Although funding can be obtained internally and externally to address developmental challenges, yet researchers seem to have mixed thoughts on funding domestic investment through external borrowing (Okoli, 2019; Adepoju, Salau & Obayelu, 2019; Malik, Hayat, 2015; Ogunmuyiwa, 2017; Oloyede, 2018; Soludo, 2018; World Bank, 2022). Some scholars claim it is insufficient, while others affirm its adequacy. Those in support claim that external borrowing will only aid infrastructure development if it is used wisely in productive activities (Malik, Hayat, 2015; Soludo, 2018). Those who advocate internal borrowing argue that it offers result to the economy and create less international burden on the need to pay back in foreign currency. This debate suggests that there is no consistency in finance literature regarding the relevance of debt for infrastructural development. Hence, the need to address this concern.

Also, this study argues for tax revenue because of its relevance as a source of revenue to the government (World Bank, 2022; UN, 2022). The advocacy is that if government channel appropriate strategy to tax creation and collection with an efficient and transparent administration it can lower government debt exposure and enhance the provision of infrastructural amenities in the country. The argument needs to be examined empirically. Although several studies have positioned the value of debt to infrastructural development, likewise how tax revenue can bolster economic growth through infrastructural development in developed and emerging economies (Aladejana, Okeowo, Oluwalana & Alabi, 2021; Adepoju, Salau & Obayelu, 2019). However, not much is known about how external debt interact with tax revenue to address infrastructural deficit in Nigeria. It is on the strength of this discussion, that this study evaluated the effect of external debt on infrastructural development in Nigeria while considering the moderating effect of tax revenue.

Literature Review

Infrastructural Development

Infrastructure is the physical installations that include things like highways and roads, airports, telecommunication facilities, water supply systems, electrical infrastructure, and waste treatment facilities, among other things (Odongo & Kalu, 2018). Infrastructure not only provides services that are included in the consumption bundles of local residents, but it also supplements both capital and labour as an input in the production process (Ayogu, 2007). Increases in investment, productivity, and long-term economic growth are all results of increased access to infrastructure provision, which is beneficial to both human development and quality of life (Ajakaiye & Ncube, 2010).

Expenditures made by Government on infrastructure are intended to raise the total amount invested in the country, which may lead to economic expansion (Ajakaiye & Ncube, 2010). In his research, Adam Smith proposed that Government should limit its spending to military, the maintenance of peace and order, and public development projects; anything beyond these is seen to be both unjust and wasteful. If the Government fails to assist with the provision of infrastructure, the economy would negatively be impacted. Communications, roadways, transportation, highways, and ports are all included in the definition of "infrastructure" (Rehman, Ilyas, Alam & Akram, 2011).

In another hypothesis, the existence of infrastructure lowers the costs of transportation and any applicable tariffs, increases access to new markets, and lowers operational expenses in a particular nation (Rehman, Ilyas, Alam & Akram, 2011). Both economic and social aspects of infrastructure are considered to be part of the larger whole (Wekesa, Wawire & Kosimbei, 2017). The former category often include facilities for transportation and communication, road building and construction, electricity generation, water supply, and sanitation, whereas the latter category comprises establishments for education and medical care (Lokesha & Mahesha, 2016). The term "infrastructural development" refers to improvements in a country's physical and non-physical infrastructure, both of which are essential to the nation's overall economic development (Lokesha & Mahesha, 2016). The improvement of infrastructure is a significant engine for economic advancement and a critical facilitator for productivity (Lokesha & Mahesha, 2017).

Government Expenditure on Agriculture

A significant contributor to the competitiveness of agricultural value chains is the agricultural infrastructure, and the key to the production of sustainably-sourced food is access to reasonably-priced physical infrastructure (Warner, Kahan & Lehel, 2008). This includes infrastructure that: supports on-farm reduction such as irrigation, energy, transportation, pre- and post-harvest storage; ensures efficient trading and exchange including telecommunications and covered markets; enables products to travel swiftly and effectively from the farm to processing facilities and on to distributors. These facilities contribute value to the domestic economy (Perovic, 2013). For example, bulk storage and transportation are two examples of this type of infrastructure.

Therefore, all of the fundamental services, facilities, equipment, and institutions that are required for the smooth operation of the food and fiber markets are included in the definition of agricultural infrastructure (Mbang, 2015). These aspects of agricultural infrastructure, either directly or indirectly, contribute to the expansion of agricultural land

and the sector's increased productivity. To achieve maximum level of agriculture's potential output, agricultural development, or its efficiency, is a multi-faceted phenomenon that requires a number of different factors and conditions to cooperate with one another (Khadaroo & Seetana, 2010). The productivity of agriculture is affected by a variety of factors, including climatic factors, the growth of agricultural infrastructure, technological advancements, agricultural inputs, and economic policies implemented by the government (Mbang, 2015).

Infrastructure is the basis upon which industrial development is built, and agricultural infrastructure is the rock-solid material foundation upon which the growth of agriculture can take place in a healthy and consistent manner. After the country gained its independence, the key to Nigeria's development, which has taken the form of a rapid economic transformation, the alleviation of poverty, and increased food security, has been the intense focus placed on agricultural development (Abubakar, Maharazu, Emmanuel & Adnan, 2018). Furthermore, historical records show that agriculture played a significant role in the economy of Nigeria. This was accomplished through the production of sufficient food and fibre of a high quality, the majority of which came from rural areas of the country (Aye, 2011). As a result, agriculture contributed the greatest share to the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) and earnings in foreign exchange. Agriculture was responsible for a total contribution of 42.07 percent to the nation's GDP in the year 2008, with crop, livestock, forestry, and fishery accounting for 37.52 percent, 2.65%, 1.37 percent, and 0.53 percent, respectively (Mbang, 2015; Abubakar, Maharazu, Emmanuel & Adnan, 2018; Aye, 2011).

As a result of this, the crop sub-sector had a contribution to the agriculture GDP that was approximately 89.2 percent. In point of fact, the majority of the early developments in the country's infrastructure were funded by the proceeds from agricultural endeavours (Olukunle, 2013). In those days, Nigeria was the world's leading exporter of groundnuts and the second-largest exporter of cocoa, accounting for approximately 36 and 20 percent of the global groundnut and cocoa trade, respectively (Ezedinachi & Orizu, 2019). The export of cotton by Nigeria accounted for approximately 18 percent of the global supply, and the country's contribution of vegetable oil represented approximately 11 percent of the global total (Abubakar, Maharazu, Emmanuel & Adnan, 2018). During this time period, Nigerian agriculture was able to grow at a rate that was sufficient to provide adequate food for the growing population as well as raw materials for the industrial sector. This led to an increase in both the public revenue and foreign exchange that the government received, as well as an increase in the number of employment opportunities available to an increasing labor force (Ezedinachi & Orizu, 2019).

In Nigeria, agriculture was responsible for approximately 60 percent of the non-oil revenue that was collected by the government (Ezedinachi & Orizu, 2019). Agricultural endeavours take place in rural communities. These rural communities experience difficulties as a result of neglect and decay of Agricultural facilities (Olukunle, 2013). The most important problem that rural farmers face is the inability to add value to their crops due to a lack of infrastructure in their areas, which is the primary cause of their lower income levels (Ezedinachi & Orizu, 2019). Because of the cumulative effects, there is now a large gap between food demand and supply, which has resulted in significant food imports which further erodes Nigeria's economy and foreign exchange earnings (Oyaniran, 2020).

The steadily increasing costs of purchasing foreign currency as a result of rising food imports over the years had knock-on effects on a variety of other aspects of the economy. This is not unconnected with the discovery of crude oil that becomes the country's major exportation. Subsequently, over 80 percent of Nigeria's earnings come from crude oil (Onawumi, Oluleye & Adebisi, 2011), with agriculture's share of the total export continuing to decline. This is unconnected with the discovery of crude oil, which later takes the centre stage of the country's exportation (Oyaniran, 2020).

However, as a result of a report published by the World Bank in 1994, the definition of agricultural infrastructure was narrowed down to include only long-lived engineered facilities and other services. These services include roads, electricity supplies, and telecommunication systems (Adams, 2021). The relationship between the development of infrastructure and agricultural productivity can be seen in the fact that agriculturally related infrastructures are anticipated to lower the costs of farmers, accelerate output, and produce more employment opportunities in the agricultural sector (Cohen, 2008). This is one way that the relationship can be seen. Infrastructure, such as roads and information and communication technology, has a direct and significant impact on agricultural productivity (Llanto, 2012). The quality of the roads has a direct correlation to the amount of agricultural production that can be achieved. Roads, electricity supplies, telecommunication, and other forms of infrastructure are important agricultural output stimulants, especially in rural areas, as was further argued by roads in the previous sentence. Peasant small holder farmers account for approximately 90 percent of all farm holdings in the country (Paulais, 2012). These farmers are the primary force behind agricultural activities. These farmers rely primarily on more conventional agricultural practices and produce food primarily for their own subsistence.

The need to provide access to input and other support to peasant farmers in order to boost their productivity and enable them to transition to mechanized agricultural practices has been a driving force behind government interventions. Commercial farm holders have been supported through the provision of credit facilities, input subsidies, capacity building initiatives, and export incentives (Adedoyin, Otekinri & Adeoti, 2016). Agriculture has continued to be a primary contributor to Nigeria's economic expansion, despite the fact that the country's overall rate of growth has slowed over time (Birdsall, Williamson & Deese, 2002). The industry expanded by 15.9 percent between the years 2000 and 2005; however, this high figure could be attributed to the enormous growth that was recorded in 2002 (55.9 percent); if that growth hadn't occurred, the industry would have expanded by 6.0 percent. Its growth, on the other hand, slowed down to 6.5 percent between the years 2006 and 2010, and 4.1 percent between 2011 and 2016, respectively (Galindo & Panizza, 201).

In a similar vein, the sector has maintained its preeminent position in the economy of Nigeria (Llanto, 2012). This is in part attributable to the contribution that the sector makes in terms of value added to GDP as well as the proportion of the population that is employed within the sector, which is estimated to be around fifty percent of all Nigerians (Adamgbe, Belonwu, Ochu & Okafor, 2020). During the years 2000-2005, this sector was responsible for 36.3% of the total value added to GDP⁷⁶. However, over the course of time, its average contribution has decreased to the point where it was only 31.7 percent during the period of 2006-2010 and further decreased to 21.3 percent during the period of 2011-2016 (Adamgbe, Belonwu, Ochu & Okafor, 2020). One of the goals that has been included in the majority of the government's agricultural policies and programmes has been to increase the nation's level of self-sufficiency, as well as to decrease the proportion of food that is imported and to encourage the export of agricultural commodities (Patel, 2014).

During the years 2000-2016, there was a consistent rise in the proportion of total merchandise exports that consisted of agricultural raw materials. These exports contributed to a higher total value. Its share increased from an insignificant 0.1 percent during the period of 2000-2005 to 1.0 percent during the period of 2006-2010 and 4.3 percent during the period of 2011-2016 respectively⁷⁸. However, significant gains that were made in reducing the share of imports of agricultural raw materials to total merchandise imports at the beginning of the period under consideration were reversed towards the end of the period. This occurred despite the fact that the beginning of the period was being considered (Patel, 2014).

Agriculture infrastructure although involves huge initial capital investments, long gestation periods, high incremental capital output ratio, high risks and low rates of returns on investments and increasing crop yields, thereby promoting agricultural growth (Patel, 2014). Government initiatives to improve the quality and quantity of infrastructure in rural areas through programmes such as the construction of small dams and boreholes for rural water supply and the clearing of feeder roads for the evacuation of agricultural produce and the supply of electricity to rural areas from large irrigation Dams, the establishment of nine River Basin Development Authorities (RBDAs) in addition to the two existing ones (Sokoto and Rima RBDAs); DFR. initiatives to increase the amount and quality of infrastructure in urban areas by implementing programs like the construction (World Bank, 1994)

External Debt

Government debt has been considered as a critical fiscal policy tool for funding a nation's growth. It is put to use in the process of settling expenditures that, in the long run, will finally boost productivity and contribute to the expansion of the economy (Muhammad, Ruhaini, Nathan & Arshad, 2017). As a result of various factors such as the decrease in oil prices, fluctuation in currency exchange rates, and rising interest rates, the global economy of developing nations has been negatively impacted, with a particularly strong effect seen in Nigeria. The problem of debt faced by numerous developing countries has received worldwide attention (Muhammad, Ruhaini, Nathan & Arshad, 2017).

The amount of a nation's total debt that is owed to entities located beyond the borders of that nation, including but not limited to multinational enterprises, international financial institutions, and overseas governments, is known as the nation's external debt (Matthew & Mordecai, 2016; Nwannebuike, Ike & Onuka, 2016; Ayadi & Ayadi, 2008). In the event that the government is unable to fulfill its responsibility of providing public goods to the populace in an effective and efficient manner in order to domestically improve the nation's standard of living and economic development, then the best alternative is to finance economic development by sourcing it from outside the nation through debt (Nwannebuike, Ike & Onuka, 2016). This sort of debt is paid off with funds derived from other countries' currencies, and interest is charged on it.

External debt refers to the amount of debt owed by a country to creditors outside of its borders. This can come from a variety of sources such as foreign companies, governments, or financial institutions (Arnone, Bandiera & Presbitero, 2005). It's not just the government that can be responsible for this type of debt, but also companies and even individuals. The

external debt constitutes a part of a nation's total debt and represents the obligations to foreign lenders (Abula, Ben & Ozovehe, 2016). The external debt of a country is the portion of its total debt that is owed to creditors residing in other countries. These creditors could be foreign commercial banks, government entities, or international financial institutions. The term "foreign debt" or "external debt" is used to describe the amount owed to these out-of-country creditors.

According to yet another interpretation of the term, external debt refers to the sum of money that the government and other organisations inside a country have borrowed from the governments and organisations of other nations (Saifuddin, 2016). The amount of money that a nation owes to other nations is known as its foreign debt. This debt might be directly owed to other nations in the form of government-to-government loans, or it can be owed indirectly as a result of a negative balance of trade (Business Dictionary, 2019).

Despite this, many countries depend on one another to support their economic development and achieve sustainable growth. This is because there is a shortage of resources and certain countries have relative advantages (Afolabi, Laoye, Kolade & Enaholo, 2017). The amount of money that a country or sub-nation owes to an international creditor after receiving financial assistance in the form of loans from that creditor is referred to as the country's or sub-external nation's debt¹⁰. This external debt can evolve into an external debt burden, which arises when the amount due gets increasingly substantial and difficult to pay back or when there is difficulties in annual debt service. Both of these scenarios are examples of situations in which an external debt burden can exist (Ali & Mshelia, 2007).

The term external debt can refer to either the national debt that is due by the government or the aggregate of borrowings by all levels of government, including the federal, state, and local levels of government (Idenyi, Igberi, Anoke, 2016). It is possible to see it as the total amount of borrowings that government bodies of a country have accumulated; this sum includes money that is owed to private companies, public entities, foreign governments, and other such entities. Therefore, it could refer to either local or foreign debt.

When discussing the national debt, it is important to take into account upcoming pension payments, existing government obligations, as well as goods and services obtained by the government using credit (Idenyi, Igberi, & Anoke, 2016). Borrowing can be a desirable option when it is utilized to finance investments that are predicted to bring in a satisfactory rate of return or to even out consumption during periods of irregular aggregate supply.

This is particularly the case when borrowing is used to fund investments that are expected to generate an adequate rate of return. By doing so, borrowing can bring about an increased level of economic well-being that would not have been possible otherwise.

However, investments that are funded by debt must be productive and efficiently managed in order to generate a rate of return that is greater than the interest or principal that is paid on the debt. (Ndekwe, 2008; Clements & Nguyen, 2008). Borrowing money from outside sources can be beneficial in that it can stimulate growth, albeit the level of this benefit is contingent on how the acquired resources are put to use. In reality, Nigeria faces limited opportunities for capital formation due to low-income levels and a high prevalence of poverty, hindering the country's ability to secure sufficient funds for development from within its own borders. The widespread nature of poverty exacerbates the situation.

When developing countries are confronted with a shortage of capital, it is typically anticipated that they will acquire external debt in order to complement their domestic saving (Ndekwe, 2008; Clements & Nguyen, 2008). Borrowing money from international financial institutions, such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), often offers interest rates that are about half as high as those offered on the home market. This makes borrowing money from abroad a more attractive option than taking on domestic debt. However, this relies on whether the borrowed money is spent in the productive sectors of the economy or if it is used for consumption, as this determines whether or not the borrowing nation would benefit from taking on external debt (Cohen, 2008).

The early authors are of the opinion that a developing country's economic progress will most likely benefit from it taking on moderate amounts of debt in order to finance its borrowing needs. If these debts are managed correctly, they can be of enormous assistance to a rising nation. Not only do they contribute to the nation's expansion, but they also increase the overall resources that are accessible to an economy over a specified time period (Ndekwe, 2008). When a loan for USD28 Million was received from the World Bank in 1958 to construct a railway and other developmental projects in Nigeria, this marked the beginning of the country's accumulation of external debt (Mbah, Agu & Umunna, 2016). The problem of servicing debt began in 1985, when the total external debt of Nigeria rose to USD19 billion. However, the government was able to pay back more than USD35 billion to the international creditors (Paris Club), while the amount of money that had been borrowed was then less than USD15 billion (Ali & Mshelia, 2007). This caused the problem of servicing debt to arise.

Due to the apparent debt overhang in Nigeria, the administration that was led by Obasanjo during the years 2003-2007 vigorously sought debt revocation, which ultimately resulted in a reduction of the country's external debt to an amount equal to USD3.4 billion in 2007 (Adedoyin, Otekinri & Adeoti, 2016). In 1964, the nation requested and received a loan from the Paris Club of Creditor Nations in the amount of \$13.1 million US dollars to fund the construction of the Niger Dam. The structure of Nigeria's debt was altered as a result of the country's participation in the International Capital Market (ICM) in 1978 for the much-talked-about "jumbo loan" of \$1 billion. Prior to this, Nigeria's debt was primarily comprised of concessional loans; after this, it was comprised of loans with more stringent repayment terms (Cohen, 2008). In 2002, Nigeria's debt reached approximately \$39.9 billion. This increase was mostly caused by the accumulation of interests, fees, and penalties in addition to the precipitous drop in oil prices. As a direct consequence of the debt crisis, Nigeria's economy grew more slowly than expected, and the country also faced increased levels of poverty and unemployment, as well as higher interest rates and security issues (Adedoyin, Otekinri & Adeoti, 2016).

Multilateral Debt

A nation's multilateral debt is the portion of its total foreign debt load that is owing to international financial institutions (IFIs) like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Mbah, Agu & Umunna, 2016). Multilateral debt is also known as multilateral obligations. As a result of the International Financial Institutions' (IFIs) status as "preferred creditors" and as providers of core development and balance-of-payment loans, multilateral debt looms larger than other obligations for the majority of the world's poorest countries (Adedoyin, Babalola, Otekinri & Adeoti, 2016). Due to the special status of these creditors, it is imperative that any payments made to them take precedence over both private and bilateral (government-to-government) debt. In addition, these organizations argue that the bylaws of their organizations prevent them from providing debt relief or writing off debts, as is common practice among commercial creditors and the government (Birdsall, Williamson & Deese, 2002).

Since IFIs determine a country's creditworthiness, governments have a special incentive to keep current on their multilateral debts: until the International Monetary Fund gives its stamp of approval, which typically requires adherence to the economic policies it recommends, poor countries generally cannot get credit or capital from other sources (Birdsall, Williamson & Deese, 2002). Also, in order to qualify for bilateral debt reduction from the countries that make up the "Paris Club" of creditors, a country must first sign onto a programme offered by the IMF. Loans and credits from the World Bank, regional

development banks, and other multilateral and intergovernmental organisations are included in the category of publicly available and publicly guaranteed multilateral loans (such as the Caribbean Development Fund, Council of Europe, European Development Fund, Islamic Development Bank, Nordic Development Fund, and similar entities) (Galindo & Panizza, 2018).

Loans from funds that are administered on behalf of a single donor government by an international organization are not eligible for this programme (Adams, 2021). These are what are known as loans from the respective governments. The primary function of multilateral financing agencies (MFAs) is to provide member nations that are in need of financial assistance with access to funds for specific projects and programmes. This, in turn, will encourage better rates of economic expansion (Galindo & Panizza, 2018). MFAs increasingly require that the institutions (and their governments) who borrow the money execute economic reforms as part of the conditions for such lending (Paulais, 2012). These requirements are becoming progressively stricter.

Therefore, the multilateral lending organizations are concerned not only with ensuring that the loans will be repaid, but also with how a particular loan affects the economy of the country and how the government will implement economic policy. Macroeconomic reform, which includes fiscal, monetary, and exchange-rate policy, as well as a recent emphasis toward market liberalisation and privatisation, is the most important issue that multilateral lending institutions take into consideration (Paulais, 2012).

Related Empirical Review

Yerima and Tahir (2020) analyzed the impact of external debt on Nigeria's agricultural production from 1980 to 2016 using secondary data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the World Development Indicators (WDI). To accomplish the aim of the research, the augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound testing approach to co-integration were used. The empirical findings showed that the variables were cointegrated, proving that they had long-run relationships in both the short and long terms. Agriculture production (AGP) was significantly positively impacted by the external debt stock (EDS), demonstrating that EDS had a positive impact on agricultural growth and that higher EDS accelerated agricultural growth over time. AGP increased by 0.96 percent for every 1 percent increase in EDS, specifically. The remaining variables showed strong and negative relationships with AGP. The results also demonstrated that EDSP had no positive effects on Nigeria's agricultural output. Aggressively pursuing the process of economic diversification through

agricultural production is a responsibility of the government. To ease the burden and adverse effects of Nigerians' excessive reliance on foreign cash from oil and the volatility in its price, there is a need to diversify the source of external debt servicing, especially to the non-oil sectors including agriculture, mining, industry, and manufacturing.

Ukpe, Umeh, Ater and Asogwa (2017) investigated the impact of state and private debt on agricultural growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2016. The fully modified ordinary least squares method was used to analyze the data that were gathered from secondary sources. The result reveals that the coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.65, meaning that public external debt, foreign direct investment, domestic private investment, and labor each accounted for 65 percent of the variation in agricultural output. The outcome also revealed that the coefficients of public external debt (-0.315) and domestic private investment (-0.488) were significant and negative, indicating that each unit increase in public external debt and domestic private investment reduces agricultural growth by 0.31 tons and 0.48 tons, respectively. Contrarily, the coefficient of labor (1.487) was significant and positive, indicating that a rise in labor productivity will result in an increase in agricultural growth of 1.487 metric tons per unit. In order to implement and assess government policies on domestic private investment, international external debt, and both, it was advised that specialized development organizations be established.

Wilson and David (2019) examined the negative impact of external debt and agricultural production in Nigeria. Using time series data from 1980 to 2017, the study goes on to assess the effect of external debt on the growth of agricultural production in Nigeria. We employed co-integration as a test instrument and ECM to look at the relationship between the variables used for this purpose. The empirical findings show that, due to its inverse relationship with agricultural production, external debt did not result in an increase in output returns in agricultural productivity. This shows that the external loans for agriculture that were obtained throughout the research period were not used to their full potential. Therefore, the study recommend that the Nigerian government show a strong commitment to effective debt management to ensure that foreign loans are channeled and used healthily for the purposes for which they were acquired. This would also guarantee that the output returns would be sufficient for the debt service obligation and balance to promote growth in other sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Theoretical Review

This research is based on the debt overhang theory which was propounded by Howard in 1972. The theory suggests that large borrowing leads to high debt, which in turn leads to

debt traps and a slowdown in economic growth. The theory directly relates to Nigeria's situation. Although the country is not among ten most indebted countries in the world, however, incidence of public debts (domestic and external debts) is high with visible small infrastructures. The concept of debt overhang posits that excessive borrowing leads to a buildup of debt, which can result in debt traps and impede economic growth. The debt overhang theory suggests that if there is a probability that the government debt will surpass a country's capacity for repayment in the future, the anticipated debt service costs will deter both domestic and foreign investment. Investors may be discouraged due to the belief that the government will increase taxes on production to service the public debt, leading to a decline in their willingness to make investments today for the purpose of enhancing future output (Akos & Istvan, 2019).

The theory posits that public debt may have nonlinear impacts on growth via the improvement of capital or the expansion of productivity. A debt overhang exists when the anticipated repayment of external debt is less than its contractual value (Spilioti & Vamvoukas, 2015). According to the debt overhang hypothesis, debt impairs economic growth by acting as a deterrent to investment and causing illiquidity. The debt stock, or the amount of debt, refers to a nation's ability to repay its debt in the long run, which is crucial for economic growth because of the disincentive posed by the debt overhang.

Methodology

The *ex-post facto* research design was used as a quantitative approach in this study to investigate the relationship between external debt, tax revenue, and infrastructure development. This study's unit of analysis is the federal government of Nigeria because the issues under consideration are macroeconomic variables for which the government is fully responsible: external debt/borrowing, tax income, and infrastructure development. The data for this study is a time series trend from 1991 to 2022. Data compiled from reports by government entities and organizations such as the CBN and the National Bureau of Statistics were used.

Model

The second model analyses the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure on agriculture in Nigeria;

The model is therefore specified as:

$$AGRIC=f(\text{extborrowing}, \text{exc}, \text{inf}, \text{int})\dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

The econometric representation of the model becomes

$$LNAGRIC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LNextborrowing_t + \beta_2 LNexc_t + \beta_3 inf_t + \beta_4 int_t + \mu_{2t} \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

Where:

$LNAGRIC_t$ = natural logarithm of government expenditure on agriculture

$LNext\ borrowing$ = natural logarithm of external borrowing

$L\ Nexc$ = the natural logarithm of exchange rate

inf = inflation rate

int = interest rate

β_0 - Constant of the regression model.

β_1 - Coefficient of log of external borrowing

β_2 - Coefficient of log of exchange rate

β_3 - Coefficient of inflation

β_4 - Coefficient of interest rate

μ_2 = Error term

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question: In what way do external borrowing affect government expenditure on agriculture in Nigeria?

Results of the ARDL model are reported in this section. This explains the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure on agriculture in Nigeria; The short and long-run estimates are presented using the ARDL framework.

Table 1: ARDL Result for Model

Dependent Variable: LNAGRIC				
Selected Model				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Statistics	Probability
LONG RUN ESTIMATES				
LNEXTBORR	-0.436	0.127	-3.421	0.003***
LNEXC	1.982	0.153	12.911	0.000*
INF	0.023	0.008	2.723	0.000***
INT	-3.486	0.019	-0.811	0.429
C	-3.486	0.398	-8.746	0.000***
SHORT RUN ESTIMATES				
D(LNAGRIC(-1))	0.328	0.137	2.398	0.029**
D(LNAGRIC(-2))	0.224	0.118	1.909	0.074*
D(LNAGRIC(-3))	0.228	0.096	2.371	0.031**
D(LNEXTBORR)	-0.041	0.163	-0.249	0.806
D(LNEXTBORR(-1))	0.364	0.178	2.043	0.058*
D(LNEXTBORR(-2))	-0.499	0.173	-2.880	0.010**

D(LNEXTBORR(-3))	0.497	0.141	3.509	0.003***
D(LNEXC)	1.748	0.277	6.303	0.000***
D(LNEXC(-1))	-1.493	0.330	-4.5170	0.000***
D(LNEXC(-2))	0.476	0.284	1.672	0.114
D(LNEXC(-3))	-0.565	0.272	-2.074	0.054*
D(INF)	-0.001	0.004	-0.312	0.759
D(INF(-1))	-0.025	0.005	-4.5613	0.000***
D(INF(-2))	-0.0135	0.005	-2.671	0.017**
D(INF(-3))	-0.028	0.005	-5.417	0.000***
CointEq(-1)*	-1.0300	0.1786	-5.7662	0.000***
R ² = 0.91				
Adjusted R ² = 0.85				
D.W. Statistics = 2.22				

Note: ***, ** and * indicate probability value at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Authors' Computation (2023)

In Table 1, the long run estimate reveals that external borrowing has a negative and significant influence on government expenditure on agriculture. A percentage increase in external borrowing will reduce government expenditure on agriculture by 0.43 percent. On the other hand, exchange rate and inflation have a significantly positive association with government expenditure on agriculture. A percentage increase in exchange rate and inflation will increase government expenditure on agriculture by 1.98 and 2 percent respectively.

For the short run estimates, one, two and three lagged values of government expenditure on agriculture significantly and positively influences the current value of government expenditure on agriculture. A percentage increase in these values will increase the current value of government expenditure on agriculture by 0.3, 0.2 and 0.2 percent respectively. External borrowing in the one, two and three lagged periods also significantly influence government expenditure on agriculture. A percentage increase in external borrowing in the one and three lagged periods will increase expenditure on agriculture by 0.36 and 0.49 percent respectively. Conversely, a percentage increase in external borrowing for the two lagged periods will reduce government expenditure on agriculture by 0.49 percent.

Exchange rate in the current and two lagged periods exert positive influence on government expenditure on agriculture, as a percentage increase in exchange rate for these periods will increase government expenditure on agriculture by 1.75 and 0.48 percent respectively. On the other hand, exchange rate in the one and three lagged periods exert negative influence on government expenditure on agriculture, as a percentage increase in exchange rate in these periods will reduce expenditure on agriculture by 1.49 and 0.56 percent respectively.

Inflation in all the periods negatively influence government expenditure on agriculture as a percentage increase in inflation in the current, one, two and three lagged periods will reduce government expenditure on agriculture by 0.1, 2.0, 1.0 and 2.0 percent respectively. The error correction term is statistically significant, negative, but greater than one. This indicates an oscillatory convergence.

Table 2: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test Model

F-Statistic	0.860	Prob. F (2,11)	0.444
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Source: Authors' Computation (2023)

Since the probability value (0.44) is greater than 0.05, we conclude that there is no evidence of serial correlation in our estimation.

Table 3: Breusch-Pagan Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test Model

F-Statistic	1.842	Prob. F(16,13)	0.109
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Source: Authors' Computation (2023)

Since the probability value (0.11) is greater than 0.05, we conclude that there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in our estimation.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the Effect of External Borrowing on Government Expenditure on Agriculture in Nigeria, while disaggregating infrastructural development into government expenditure on agriculture. This estimated the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure on agriculture in Nigeria, the model was also analysed within the ARDL framework and estimates were obtained in both the short and long run.

The long run estimate reveals that external borrowing has a negative and significant influence on government expenditure on agriculture. This still aligns with the findings from the first objective analysed by not conforming to a-priori expectation. The reasons for this are not far-fetched, external borrowings invested in the agricultural sector are not properly utilized and monitored. This aligns with findings of previous studies (Idenyi, Igberi & Anoke, 2016; Amaefule & Umeaka, 2016). But deviates from findings of another study (Osadume & Imide, 2022). On the other hand, exchange rate and inflation have a significantly positive association with government expenditure on agriculture. The positive relationship with exchange rate and inflation with government expenditure on agriculture can be explained by the fact that inflation experienced in Nigeria over the years has been classified as imported inflation and as such in a bid to reduce this, government has been looking inwards to develop the agricultural sector of the country as an import-substitution strategy. An example of this is the Anchor Borrower's Programme of the CBN. This also explains the positive relationship with exchange rate and government expenditure on agriculture. Following the huge demand for exchange rates over the years, the government through the CBN banned the importation of certain food items and began to invest heavily in the agricultural sector.

For the short run estimates, external borrowing in the one, two and three lagged periods also significantly influence government expenditure on agriculture. This conforms to a-priori expectation as it shows that external borrowing has helped in boosting the level of agricultural development of the country.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study evaluated the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure on agriculture in Nigeria. It precisely examined the effect of external borrowing on government expenditure on agriculture and community services such as education,

health, security, and water respectively. Secondary data were sourced from World Bank, NBS, and CBN reports from 1981-2021 to achieve the objectives of this study. Following from the interpretation of analyses of data collected and findings of the study.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Government should aggressively pursue the process of diversification of the economy through agricultural production.
- ii. There is need to diversify the source of external debt service especially to the non-oil sectors such as agriculture, mines, industry and manufacturing, to reduce the burden and the negative consequences of over dependence on foreign exchange from oil and the volatility in its price on Nigerians.
- iii. The study calls for stringent measures in monitoring, evaluation, accountability and transparency in the loan disbursement and utilization.
- iv. The study suggests that external borrowing exerts negative but significant effect of agriculture in Nigeria.

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